

Versioned Archive and Review of Biotic
Interactions and Taxon Names Found within
hurlbertlab/dietdatabase
hash://md5/54a9e545a68e6842dfbaee29a08061e6

by Nomer, Elton and Preston, three naive review bots
review@globalbioticinteractions.org
<https://globalbioticinteractions.org/contribute>

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Abstract

Life on Earth is sustained by complex interactions between organisms and their environment. These biotic interactions can be captured in datasets and published digitally. We present a review and archiving process for such an openly accessible digital interactions dataset of known origin and discuss its outcome. The dataset under review, named `hurlbertlab/dietdatabase`, has fingerprint hash://md5/54a9e545a68e6842dfbaee29a08061e6, is 45.2MiB in size and contains 75,101 interactions with 1 unique type of association (e.g., eats) between 767 primary taxa (e.g., *Bubulcus ibis*) and 7,196 associated taxa (e.g., Animalia). This report includes detailed summaries of interaction data, a taxonomic review from multiple catalogs, and an archived version of the dataset from which the reviews are derived.

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Introduction

Data Review and Archive

Data review and archiving can be a time-consuming process, especially when done manually. This review report aims to help facilitate both activities. It automates the archiving of datasets, including Darwin Core archives, and is a citable backup of a version of the dataset. Additionally, an automatic review of species interaction claims made in the dataset is generated and registered with Global Biotic Interactions (J. H. Poelen, Simons, and Mungall 2014).

This review includes summary statistics about, and observations about, the dataset under review :

Hurlbert, A. H., Olsen, A. M., Sawyer, M. M., and Winner, P. M.
 2021. Avian Diet Database. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5151056>
<https://github.com/hurlbertlab/dietdatabase/archive/015b00a098e06e9dbca04ad878fcf4468797e03a.zip>
 2026-06-06T13:52:48.052Z hash://md5/54a9e545a68e6842dfbaee29a08061e6

Methods

The review is performed through programmatic scripts that leverage tools like Preston (Elliott et al. 2025), Elton (Kuhn, Poelen, and Leinweber 2025), Nomer (Salim and Poelen 2025), globinizer (J. Poelen, Seltmann, and Mietchen 2024) combined with third-party tools like grep, mlr, tail and head.

Table 1: Tools used in this review process

tool name	version
preston	0.11.1
elton	0.16.11

tool name	version
nomer	0.6.5
globinizer	0.4.0
mlr	6.0.0
jq	1.6
yq	4.25.3
pandoc	3.1.6.1
duckdb	1.3.1
mapserver	7.6.4

The review process can be described in the form of the script below ¹.

```
# get versioned copy of the dataset (size approx. 45.2MiB) under review
elton pull hurlbertlab/dietdatabase

# generate review notes
elton review hurlbertlab/dietdatabase \
> review.tsv

# export indexed interaction records
elton interactions hurlbertlab/dietdatabase \
> interactions.tsv

# export names and align them with the Catalogue of Life using Nomer
elton names hurlbertlab/dietdatabase \
| nomer append col \
> name-alignment.tsv
```

or visually, in a process diagram.

Figure 1: Review Process Overview

You can find a copy of the full review script at [check-data.sh](#). See also [GitHub](#) and [Codeberg](#).

¹Note that you have to first get the data (e.g., via `elton pull hurlbertlab/dietdatabase`) before being able to generate reviews (e.g., `elton review hurlbertlab/dietdatabase`), extract interaction claims (e.g., `elton interactions hurlbertlab/dietdatabase`), or list taxonomic names (e.g., `elton names hurlbertlab/dietdatabase`)

Results

In the following sections, the results of the review are summarized ². Then, links to the detailed review reports are provided.

Files

An extensive list of files produced as part of the review process can be found in Appendix A. Review Files.

Archived Dataset

Note that *data.zip* file in this archive contains the complete, unmodified archived dataset under review.

Biotic Interactions

Figure 2: Biotic Interaction Data Model

In this review, biotic interactions (or biotic associations) are modeled as a primary (aka subject, source) organism interacting with an associate (aka object, target) organism. The dataset under review classified the primary/associate organisms with specific taxa. The primary and associate organisms The kind of interaction is documented as an interaction type.

The dataset under review, named *hurlbertlab/dietdatabase*, has fingerprint hash://md5/54a9e545a68e6842dfbaee29a08061e6, is 45.2MiB in size and contains 75,101 interactions with 1 unique type of association (e.g., eats) between 767 primary taxa (e.g., *Bubulcus ibis*) and 7,196 associated taxa (e.g., Animalia).

An exhaustive list of indexed interaction claims can be found in gzipped csv, tsv, geopackage and parquet archives. To facilitate discovery, a preview of claims available in the gzipped html page at [indexed-interactions.html.gz](#) are shown below.

The exhaustive list was used to create the following data summaries below.

²Disclaimer: The results in this review should be considered friendly, yet naive, notes from an unsophisticated robot. Please keep that in mind when considering the review results.

Table 2: Sample of Indexed Interaction Claims

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Haliaeetus leucocephalus	eats	Ictalurus	Brown, B. T., W. C. Leibfried, T. R. Huels, and J. A. Olivera. 1991. Prey remains from Bald Eagle nests in Sonora, Mexico. <i>Southwestern Naturalist</i> 36:259-262.
Haliaeetus leucocephalus	eats	Cyprinus carpio	Brown, B. T., W. C. Leibfried, T. R. Huels, and J. A. Olivera. 1991. Prey remains from Bald Eagle nests in Sonora, Mexico. <i>Southwestern Naturalist</i> 36:259-262.
Haliaeetus leucocephalus	eats	Carpoides carpio	Brown, B. T., W. C. Leibfried, T. R. Huels, and J. A. Olivera. 1991. Prey remains from Bald Eagle nests in Sonora, Mexico. <i>Southwestern Naturalist</i> 36:259-262.

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Haliaeetus leucocephalus	eats	Catostomus	Brown, B. T., W. C. Leibfried, T. R. Huels, and J. A. Olivera. 1991. Prey remains from Bald Eagle nests in Sonora, Mexico. Southwestern Naturalist 36:259-262.

Table 3: Most Frequently Mentioned Interaction Types (up to 20 most frequent)

interactionTypeName	count
eats	75101

Table 4: Most Frequently Mentioned Primary Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	count
Bubulcus ibis	3274
Phalacrocorax auritus	2713
Phalacrocorax carbo	1999
Bubo virginianus	1410
Haliaeetus leucocephalus	1217
Tyto alba	1149
Zenaida asiatica	1123
Bonasa umbellus	946
Aquila chrysaetos	893
Meleagris gallopavo	876
Centrocercus urophasianus	835
Asio otus	732
Anous minutus	611
Buteo jamaicensis	594
Sturnella neglecta	555
Accipiter cooperii	530
Egretta caerulea	520
Vireo olivaceus	480

sourceTaxonName	count
Turdus migratorius	469

Table 5: Most Frequently Mentioned Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

targetTaxonName	count
Animalia	1771
Magnoliopsida	1763
Coleoptera	1686
Lepidoptera	1562
Insecta	1317
Tracheophyta	1301
Chordata	1149
Hymenoptera	962
Araneae	939
Diptera	873
Orthoptera	791
Hemiptera	713
Arthropoda	673
Poaceae	665
Cephalopoda	650
Aves	603
Formicidae	559
Curculionidae	433
Gastropoda	394

Table 6: Most Frequent Interactions between Primary and Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	count
Phalacrocorax auritus	eats	Perca flavescens	185
Zenaida asiatica	eats	Magnoliopsida	133
Tetrao urogallus	eats	Pinus sylvestris	128
Phalacrocorax auritus	eats	Alosa pseudoharengus	115
Bubulcus ibis	eats	Araneae	111
Bubulcus ibis	eats	Lepidoptera	107
Phalacrocorax auritus	eats	Cyprinidae	107
Bubulcus ibis	eats	Diptera	97
Bubo virginianus	eats	Sylvilagus	96
Phalacrocorax auritus	eats	Animalia	95

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	count
Tetrao urogallus	eats	Vaccinium myrtillus	91
Tyto alba	eats	Peromyscus	89
Bubulcus ibis	eats	Orthoptera	86
Phalacrocorax auritus	eats	Micropterus dolomieu	82
Bubulcus ibis	eats	Coleoptera	81
Phalacrocorax carbo	eats	Rutilus rutilus	78
Phalacrocorax auritus	eats	Morone americana	78
Bubo virginianus	eats	Peromyscus	77
Phalacrocorax auritus	eats	Lepomis	77

Interaction Networks

The figures below provide a graph view on the dataset under review. The first shows a summary network on the kingdom level, and the second shows how interactions on the family level. It is important to note that both network graphs were first aligned taxonomically using the Catalogue of Life. Please refer to the original (or verbatim) taxonomic names for a more original view on the interaction data.

You can download the indexed dataset under review at indexed-interactions.csv.gz. A tab-separated file can be found at indexed-interactions.tsv.gz.

Geospatial Distribution

If geospatial information was extracted from the dataset under review, the map below will show their distribution. These maps were generated using MapServer (McKenna et al. 2025) tools configured via map configuration `indexed-interactions.map` :

```
MAP
  SIZE 1600 800
  EXTENT -180 -90 180 90
  PROJECTION
    "init=epsg:4326"
  END
  LAYER # MODIS WMS map from NASA
    NAME "modis_nasa"
    TYPE RASTER
    OFFSITE 0 0 0
    STATUS ON
    CONNECTIONTYPE WMS
    CONNECTION "https://gibs.earthdata.nasa.gov/wms/epsg4326/best/wms.cgi?"

  METADATA
    "wms_srs" "EPSG:4326"
```


Figure 3: Interactions on taxonomic kingdom rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life download svg

Figure 4: Interactions on the taxonomic family rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life. [download svg](#)

```

        "wms_name" "OSM_Land_Water_Map"
        "wms_server_version" "1.1.1"
        "wms_format" "image/jpeg"
    END
    CLASS
        STYLE
            COLOR          232 232 232
            OUTLINECOLOR  32 32 32
        END
    END
END
LAYER
    NAME "indexed-interactions"
    TYPE POLYGON
    STATUS ON
    CONNECTIONTYPE OGR
    CONNECTION "indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg"
    DATA "indexed-interactions-h3"
    CLASS
        STYLE
            COLORRANGE 253.0 231.0 37.0 32.0 164.0 134.0
            DATARANGE 0.3010299956639812 2.8305886686851442
            RANGEITEM "log_number_of_records"
            OUTLINECOLOR 0 0 0
        END
    END
END
END

```

Associated data can be found in the geopackage files at indexed-interactions.gpkg for point data and indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg for data clustered in geospatial h3 hexagonals.

Learn more about the structure of this download at GloBI website, by opening a GitHub issue, or by sending an email.

Another way to discover the dataset under review is by searching for it on the GloBI website.

Taxonomic Alignment

As part of the review, all names are aligned against various name catalogs (e.g., col, ncbi, discoverlife, gbif, itis, wfo, mdd, tpt, pbdb, and worms). These alignments can help review name usage or aid in selecting of a suitable taxonomic name resource.

Figure 5: Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

Table 7: Sample of Name Alignments

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
<i>Acanthis flammea</i>	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	col	<i>Acanthis flammea</i>
<i>Accipiter cooperii</i>	SYNONYM_OF	col	<i>Astur cooperii</i>
<i>Accipiter gentilis</i>	SYNONYM_OF	col	<i>Astur gentilis</i>
<i>Accipiter striatus</i>	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	col	<i>Accipiter striatus</i>

Table 8: Distribution of Taxonomic Ranks of Aligned Names by Catalog. Names that were not aligned with a catalog are counted as NAs. So, the total number of unaligned names for a catalog will be listed in their NA row.

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	NA	93
col	class	33
col	family	635
col	genus	1787
col	gigaclass	1
col	infraorder	1
col	infratribe	1
col	kingdom	4
col	order	83

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	parvorder	1
col	phylum	16
col	species	4955
col	subfamily	14
col	subgenus	59
col	suborder	24
col	subspecies	84
col	subtribe	4
col	superfamily	2
col	superorder	2
col	tribe	27
col	variety	15
discoverlife	NA	7604
discoverlife	species	30
gbif	NA	107
gbif	class	35
gbif	family	639
gbif	genus	1803
gbif	kingdom	4
gbif	order	84
gbif	phylum	15
gbif	species	4964
gbif	subspecies	90
gbif	variety	26
itis	NA	459
itis	class	33
itis	division	6
itis	family	631
itis	genus	1654
itis	infrakingdom	1
itis	kingdom	5
itis	order	93
itis	phylum	9
itis	species	4702
itis	subclass	2
itis	subfamily	1
itis	subgenus	1
itis	subkingdom	1
itis	suborder	30
itis	subspecies	6
itis	superclass	1
itis	superdivision	1
itis	superfamily	2
itis	superorder	2

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
itis	variety	3
mdd	NA	7633
ncbi	NA	716
ncbi	clade	4
ncbi	class	30
ncbi	cohort	1
ncbi	family	629
ncbi	genus	1713
ncbi	infraorder	2
ncbi	kingdom	2
ncbi	order	87
ncbi	phylum	13
ncbi	series	1
ncbi	species	4400
ncbi	subclass	1
ncbi	subfamily	3
ncbi	subgenus	33
ncbi	suborder	25
ncbi	subspecies	5
ncbi	superclass	1
ncbi	superfamily	1
ncbi	superorder	2
ncbi	varietas	1
pdb	NA	4629
pdb	class	33
pdb	family	603
pdb	genus	1070
pdb	infraclass	2
pdb	infraorder	5
pdb	kingdom	4
pdb	order	90
pdb	phylum	13
pdb	species	1156
pdb	subclass	3
pdb	subfamily	4
pdb	suborder	27
pdb	superclass	1
pdb	superfamily	3
pdb	superorder	2
pdb	superphylum	1
pdb	tribe	2
pdb	unranked clade	20
tpt	NA	6342
tpt	family	51

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
tpt	genus	152
tpt	order	11
tpt	species	1077
wfo	NA	5829
wfo	family	58
wfo	genus	495
wfo	order	7
wfo	species	1234
wfo	subspecies	16
wfo	variety	6
worms	NA	3906
worms	class	31
worms	family	523
worms	genus	1000
worms	gigaclass	1
worms	infraorder	1
worms	kingdom	4
worms	order	80
worms	phylum	10
worms	phylum (division)	6
worms	species	2050
worms	subclass	2
worms	suborder	18
worms	subspecies	3
worms	superclass	1
worms	superfamily	1
worms	superorder	3
worms	variety	4

Table 9: Name relationship types per catalog. Name relationship type “NONE” means that a name was not recognized by the associated catalog. “SAME_AS” indicates either a “HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME” or “SYNONYM_OF” name relationship type. We recognize that “SYNONYM_OF” encompasses many types of nomenclatural synonymies (ICZN 1999) (e.g., junior synonym, senior synonyms).

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
col	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	8033
col	SYNONYM_OF	1787
col	NONE	95
discoverlife	NONE	7979

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
discoverlife	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	28
discoverlife	SYNONYM_OF	7
discoverlife	HOMONYM_OF	2
gbif	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	8706
gbif	NONE	109
gbif	SYNONYM_OF	1864
itis	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	7504
itis	NONE	459
itis	SYNONYM_OF	240
mdd	NONE	7809
mdd	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	194
mdd	SYNONYM_OF	5
ncbi	SAME_AS	7156
ncbi	NONE	721
ncbi	SYNONYM_OF	226
pbdb	NONE	4704
pbdb	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	3297
pbdb	SYNONYM_OF	197
tpt	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1596
tpt	NONE	6401
tpt	SYNONYM_OF	12
wfo	NONE	6198
wfo	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1727
wfo	SYNONYM_OF	265
wfo	HAS_UNCHECKED_NAME	157
worms	NONE	3999
worms	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	3894
worms	SYNONYM_OF	320

Table 10: List of Available Name Alignment Reports

catalog name	alignment results
col	associated names alignments report in zipped html, csv, and tsv)
ncbi	associated names alignments report in zipped html, csv, and tsv)
discoverlife	associated names alignments report in zipped html, csv, and tsv)
gbif	associated names alignments report in zipped html, csv, and tsv)
itis	associated names alignments report in zipped html, csv, and tsv)

catalog name	alignment results
wfo	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
mdd	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
tpt	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
pbdb	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
worms	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

Additional Reviews

Elton, Nomer, and other tools may have difficulties interpreting existing species interaction datasets. Or, they may misbehave, or otherwise show unexpected behavior. As part of the review process, detailed review notes are kept that document possibly misbehaving, or confused, review bots. An sample of review notes associated with this review can be found below.

Table 11: First few lines in the review notes.

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-06-08T19:05:03Z	note	Unrecognized token 'org': was expecting (JSON String, Number, Array, Object or token 'null', 'true' or 'false') at [Source: (String)"org.eol.globi.domain.StudyImpl@3b6ddd1d"; line: 1, column: 4]
2026-06-08T19:05:03Z	note	Unrecognized token 'org': was expecting (JSON String, Number, Array, Object or token 'null', 'true' or 'false') at [Source: (String)"org.eol.globi.domain.StudyImpl@1da2cb77"; line: 1, column: 4]

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-06-08T19:05:03Z	note	Unrecognized token 'org': was expecting (JSON String, Number, Array, Object or token 'null', 'true' or 'false') at [Source: (String)"org.eol.globi.domain.StudyImpl@48f278eb"; line: 1, column: 4]
2026-06-08T19:05:03Z	note	Unrecognized token 'org': was expecting (JSON String, Number, Array, Object or token 'null', 'true' or 'false') at [Source: (String)"org.eol.globi.domain.StudyImpl@2f217633"; line: 1, column: 4]

In addition, you can find the most frequently occurring notes in the table below.

Table 12: Most frequently occurring review notes, if any.

reviewComment	count
Unrecognized token 'org': was expecting (JSON String, Number, Array, Object or token 'null', 'true' or 'false') at [Source: (String)"org.eol.globi.domain.StudyImpl@3b6ddd1d"; line: 1, column: 4]	1
Unrecognized token 'org': was expecting (JSON String, Number, Array, Object or token 'null', 'true' or 'false') at [Source: (String)"org.eol.globi.domain.StudyImpl@1da2cb77"; line: 1, column: 4]	1
Unrecognized token 'org': was expecting (JSON String, Number, Array, Object or token 'null', 'true' or 'false') at [Source: (String)"org.eol.globi.domain.StudyImpl@48f278eb"; line: 1, column: 4]	1

reviewComment	count
Unrecognized token 'org': was expecting (JSON String, Number, Array, Object or token 'null', 'true' or 'false') at [Source: (String)"org.eol.globi.domain.StudyImpl@2f217633"; line: 1, column: 4]	1

For additional information on review notes, please have a look at the first 500 Review Notes in html format or the download full gzipped csv or tsv archives.

GloBI Review Badge

As part of the review, a review badge is generated. This review badge can be included in webpages to indicate the review status of the dataset under review.

Figure 6: Picture of a GloBI Review Badge ³

Note that if the badge is green, no review notes were generated. If the badge is yellow, the review bots may need some help with interpreting the species interaction data.

GloBI Index Badge

If the dataset under review has been registered with GloBI, and has been successfully indexed by GloBI, the GloBI Index Status Badge will turn green. This means that the dataset under review was indexed by GloBI and is available through GloBI services and derived data products.

Figure 7: Picture of a GloBI Index Badge ⁴

If you'd like to keep track of reviews or index status of the dataset under review, please visit GloBI's dataset index ⁵ for badge examples.

³Up-to-date status of the GloBI Review Badge can be retrieved from the GloBI Review Depot

⁴Up-to-date status of the GloBI Index Badge can be retrieved from GloBI's API

⁵At time of writing (2026-06-08) the version of the GloBI dataset index was available at <https://globalbioticinteractions.org/datasets>

Discussion

This review and archive provides a means of creating citable versions of datasets that change frequently. This may be useful for dataset managers, including natural history collection data managers, as a backup archive of a shared Darwin Core archive. It also serves as a means of creating a trackable citation for the dataset in an automated way, while also including some information about the contents of the dataset.

This review aims to provide a perspective on the dataset to aid in understanding of species interaction claims discovered. However, it is important to note that this review does *not* assess the quality of the dataset. Instead, it serves as an indication of the open-ness⁶ and FAIRness (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Trekels et al. 2023) of the dataset: to perform this review, the data was likely openly available, **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable. The current Open-FAIR assessment is qualitative, and a more quantitative approach can be implemented with specified measurement units.

This report also showcases the reuse of machine-actionable (meta)data, something highly recommended by the FAIR Data Principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Making (meta)data machine-actionable enables more precise processing by computers, enabling even naive review bots like Nomer and Elton to interpret the data effectively. This capability is crucial for not just automating the generation of reports, but also for facilitating seamless data exchanges, promoting interoperability.

Acknowledgements

We thank the many humans that created us and those who created and maintained the data, software and other intellectual resources that were used for producing this review. In addition, we are grateful for the natural resources providing the basis for these human and bot activities. Also, thanks to <https://github.com/zygoballus> for helping improve the layout of the review tables.

Author contributions

Nomer was responsible for name alignments. Elton carried out dataset extraction, and generated the review notes. Preston tracked, versioned, and packaged, the dataset under review.

⁶According to <http://opendefinition.org/>: “Open data is data that can be freely used, reused and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike.”

Appendix A. Review Files

The following files are produced in this review:

filename	description
biblio.bib	list of bibliographic reference of this review
check-dataset.sh	data review workflow/process as expressed in a bash script
data.zip	a versioned archive of the data under review
HEAD	the digital signature of the data under review
index.docx	review in MS Word format
index.html	review in HTML format
index.md	review in Pandoc markdown format
index.pdf	review in PDF format
indexed-citations.csv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped comma-separated values file format
indexed-citations.html.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interactions claims in gzipped html file format
indexed-citations.tsv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions-col-family-col-family.svg	network diagram showing the taxon family to taxon family interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions-col-kingdom-col-kingdom.svg	network diagram showing the taxon kingdom to taxon kingdom interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions.csv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-interactions.html.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-interactions.tsv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions.parquet	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-interactions.png	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review plotted on a map
indexed-interactions.map	mapserver configuration to plot species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review on a map
indexed-interactions.gpkg	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg	geospatially clustered h3 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-sample.csv	list of species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions-sample.html	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in html format
indexed-interactions-sample.tsv	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
indexed-names.csv.gz	taxonomic names indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-names.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-col.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-col.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-itis.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-worms.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-sample.csv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
indexed-names-sample.html	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in html format
indexed-names-sample.tsv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
interaction.svg	diagram summarizing the data model used to index species interaction claims
nanopub-sample.trig	first 500 species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)

filename	description
nanopub.trig.gz	species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
process.svg	diagram summarizing the data review processing workflow
prov.nq	origin of the dataset under review as expressed in rdf/nquads
review.csv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
review.html.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped html format
review.tsv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
review-sample.csv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
review-sample.html	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in html format
review-sample.tsv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
review.svg	a review badge generated as part of the dataset review process
zenodo.json	metadata of this review expressed in Zenodo record metadata

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